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Gross Disposable Income Per Capita in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2021

It grew on average by 17.99%

Istat calculates the value of gross disposable income per capita. The variable is defined as the ratio between gross disposable income of consumer families and the total number of resident people. The data refers to the period 2004 and 2021 for the 20 Italian regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of gross disposable income in 2021. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place by value of gross disposable income per capita in 2021 with a value of 24,324.00 euros, followed by Lombardy with an amount of 23,862.30 euros, and from Emilia Romagna with a value of 23,288.30 euros. In the middle of the table are Veneto with an amount of 20,999.60 euros, followed by Tuscany with an amount of 20,746.00 euros, and Marche with an amount of 20,746.00 euros. Sicily closes the ranking with an amount of 14,763.80 euros, followed by Campania with an amount of 14,512.00 euros and Calabria with an amount of 14,108.10 euros.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in gross disposable income in the Italian regions between 2004 and 2021. Sardinia is in first place for the value of the percentage change in gross disposable income with a value equal to 32.30% corresponding to a change from an amount of 12,742.70 euros up to 16,859.10 euros or equal to an amount of 4,116.40 euros. Basilicata follows with a variation equal to an amount of 28.21% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 12,270.40 euros up to a value of 15,732.20 euros or equal to an amount of 3,461.80 euros. Puglia follows with a percentage variation of 28.21% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 12,164.20 euros up to 15,392.40 euros corresponding to a value of 3,228.20 euros. In the middle of the ranking is Trentino Alto Adige with a variation equal to 20.00% equal to a variation from an amount of 20,269.90 euros up to a value of 24,324.00 euros equal to an amount of 4,054.10 euros. Veneto follows with a variation equal to an amount of 18.95% equal to a variation from 17,654.20 euros up to a value of 20,999.60 euros equal to an amount of 3,345.40 euros. Below is Campania with a value of 18.35% equal to a variation from an amount of 12,262.00 euros equal to an amount of 14,512.50 euros equal to a value of +2,250.50 euros. Tuscany closes the ranking with a value of 11.49% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 18,608.90 euros up to a value of 20,746.60 euros equal to an amount of 2,137.70 euros. Umbria follows with a variation equal to 10.83% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 17,394.70 euros up to a value of 19,277.70 euros equal to an amount of 1,883.00 euros. Finally, Valle d'Aosta with a variation equal to an amount of 10.76% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 19,494.40 euros up to a value of 21,592.70 euros equal to an amount of 2,098.30 euros. On average, the value of gross disposable income in the Italian regions between 2004 and 2021 grew from an amount of 16,297.77 euros to a value of 19,229.88 euros or equal to an amount of 2,932.11 euros equal to an amount of 17.99%.

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Gross disposable income per capita in the Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2021. Gross disposable income per capita grew in almost all Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2021. In particular, it grew in the North for an amount of 16.12%, in the North-West for an amount of 16.00%, in the North-East for 16.33%, in the Center for 12.83%, in the South for an amount of 23.75%, in the South for a value of 22.24%, in the Islands for an amount of 27.01%. We can note that the value of gross disposable income per capita has grown especially in the southern regions. This growth is due to the fact that generally economic areas that have low per capita incomes tend to grow in percentage terms. However, the phenomenon of income convergence between southern and northern regions does not occur in absolute terms, even if the percentage growth rates of the southern regions tend to be higher than the northern regions.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The data shows the presence of two clusters:

- Cluster 1: Basilicata, Puglia, Sicily, Campania, Calabria, Molise, Sardinia, Abruzzo;
- Cluster 2: Piedmont, Liguria, Valle d'Aosta, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Lazio, Tuscany, Emilia Romagna, Lombardy, Trentino Alto Adige, Veneto, Umbria, Marche.

From the point of view of the clusters we can note the following ordering: C2>C1. Specifically, we can note that in the Central-Northern regions there is a much higher level of gross disposable income per capita than in the southern regions. From the point of view of per capita income, the distinction between central-northern regions and southern regions is clear. That is, the clustering corresponding exactly to a geographical and institutional distinction.

Conclusions. Gross disposable income per capita grew on average in all regions. In percentage terms, the southern regions experienced significant growth between 2004 and 2021 even if the per capita income of the southern regions is reduced compared to the northern regions. However, there is a significant gap between southern regions and central-northern regions in terms of gross per capita income. It follows that the economic policies of economic convergence between southern and northern regions appear to be a failure. Italy appears to be substantially divided between southern regions and northern regions in terms of per capita income. It therefore follows that in the absence of adequate forms of redistribution it will be very difficult for southern Italy to compete both in the Mediterranean and in Europe in the absence of adequate investments. If we add that Southern Italy also suffers from demographic issues essentially connected to the aging of the population and the emigration of young people, then we can easily understand how unsuccessful the economic policies for the promotion of the Southern economy have been. Italy remains a country divided in two. And it is highly unlikely that Italy will be able to remain among the countries that count in Europe and globally in the absence of adequate policies for the economic and social development of the South.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

